

The Influence of Community of Practice, Knowledge Capturing, and Knowledge Sharing on the Employees Performance

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Abstract:- This study aims to determine the impact of Community of Practice, Knowledge Capturing, and Knowledge Sharing at the same time on employee performance of PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor and find the most dominant influence among independent variables that will then be made a priority of improvement to improve employee performance. This research used a survey method with the quantitative and descriptive study. The research sample was 30 employees of PT. PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor . Data analysis used Multiple Linear Regression with SPSS 25. This study found a positive and significant influence between Community of Practice, Knowledge Capturing dan Knowledge Sharing on employee performance of PT. PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor. The influence of Knowledge Sharing is more dominant than the power of the other two variables. So that improvements in efforts to motivate employees' work are a priority to improve employee performance.

Keywords:- Knowledge Management, Community of Practice, Knowledge Capturing dan Knowledge Sharing, Performance Introduction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources in a company are an essential factor in the sustainability of a company. Companies expect to be able to improve the performance of employees to compete. HR issues are a particular concern for companies to survive. The company is expected to develop, acquire, and maintain human resources that have the best quality. PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor is a company engaged in electrical transmission maintenance services. Therefore the resources with the skills and abilities needed by this company are significant to prevent maintenance failures that cause power outages for customers and minimize the risk of work accidents. This creates differences in skills and differences between employees in the company's work environment.

According to Hersey and Blanchard in the journal Haris and Labusab (2016), employee performance is the function and ability to complete orders or tasks. A person must have a certain level of knowledge. Based on the pre-research conducted by researchers by distributing it to 10 employees of UPT PT PLN (Persero) Bogor. There are still problems related to the community of practice, knowledge capture, knowledge sharing, and employee performance.

The performance of PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor employees is still far from the excellent category. This is also confirmed by the decline in employee performance for two semesters in the last five years. From the results of Figure 1, researchers have evaluated during the previous semester that this company has problems that arise in each division in carrying out their performance. Employees often have difficulty equating perceptions in solving existing problems, which is also due to problems that the division has not previously faced. New problems that arise and there is no solution to the problem occur because of a lack of experience in solving these problems.

According to Ahmad (2017), knowledge management will have a significant positive effect on company performance, and this means that the higher the knowledge management, the higher the company's performance and the effect on employee performance. So that knowledge management is needed in every company that develops its human resources. This is done in order to distribute knowledge to every human resource in the company to improve the skills and knowledge of employees. Everyone has different abilities. The amount of knowledge and expertise in each individual may not be what the company wants. Therefore it is a better step for the company to carry out management to know what to do and how to do it.

Ahmad's research, 2017 states that knowledge management significantly affects employee performance and company performance. Knowledge management consists of Community of Practice, Knowledge Capturing, and Knowledge Sharing. However, when it turns into reality, the three conditions of control still have shortcomings, so their performance is not optimal. There are still many employees who are not enthusiastic about an activity/forum created by the company, and employees of PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor are still unable to use the previous knowledge that the company has in helping to complete the work. From the reality on the ground, there are still many company performance values that have not been achieved. This is due to employee performance that has not been maximized.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

The company will look advanced if it has employees who have high qualifications in carrying out their performance. Performance is assessed from the aspect and in terms of quality and quantity obtained by workers in carrying out their obligations to carry out the tasks assigned and charged to them according to their responsibilities. (Mangkunegara, 2013). One method to improve performance is knowledge management. Dalkir (2011:5) states that knowledge management is a collaborative and integrated approach in creating, accessing, managing, using, and capturing the company's intellectual assets. In contrast, the purpose of knowledge management is to develop and maintain personal knowledge and change these assets in a form that is easier to understand and share for workers in a company so that knowledge management can be concluded as a process of creating, managing, identifying, and disseminating knowledge so that can be understood and used again in a company.

There are four processes in knowledge management: creation, assimilation, dissemination, and application of knowledge within a company (Tjakraatmadja et al., 2015). From the knowledge management process, there are various programs carried out by PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor in carrying out its knowledge management, some of which are Community of Practice,

Knowledge Capturing and Knowledge Sharing. Knowledge creation in the Community of Practice occurs when individuals share the knowledge needed to solve problems. New knowledge can be created through explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge as a social process among individuals. (Wenger in the journal Ilpo Pohjola, 2015). Tacit knowledge is mapped in the brain or imprinted on a person obtained from experience and work. At the same time, explicit knowledge is all forms of knowledge that have been documented and recorded to make managing and distributing it easier (Lumbantobing, 2016).

This is what underlies knowledge capturing, where tacit knowledge that has been embedded in a person is converted into explicit knowledge to make it easier to share with others. In other words, knowledge capturing is the process of tacit knowledge into clear knowledge. Knowledge capture is a step in the process of finding and observing existing knowledge inside or outside the company. The knowledge that is useful for the company will be continued in the knowledge-sharing process. Knowledge Sharing is a step and function within the company where individuals exchange ideas and knowledge integration and produce a new understanding. Companies and employees share knowledge intending to build the company's goal of achieving a competitive advantage. (Aulawi in the journal Laily and Ernawati, 2020).

A. *The influence between Community of Practice (X1) and Employee Performance (Y)*

Community of Practice itself is a group discussion that contains a group of individuals who share experiences and solve problems that result in innovation. The work experience gained will improve employee performance. According to Sudirman, M. (2019) research, there is a significant simultaneous influence between knowledge and ability and experience variables on employee performance variables.

B. *The influence between Knowledge Capturing (X2) and Employee Performance (Y)*

Knowledge capturing is the concept of changing tacit knowledge from employees' experiences into explicit knowledge to make it easier to learn. It makes it easier for other employees to learn it. Thus, by increasing employee knowledge, they can maximize the performance of the employee concerned. They were based on the results of research by Tamara, P. D. A. (2019), which states that the employee knowledge variable shows a positive and significant effect, which means that employee knowledge contributes to improving employee performance.

C. *The influence between Knowledge Sharing (X3) and Employee Performance (Y)*

Community The results of the CL study. Safitri, SW. LH. Setyanti, Sudarsih (2018) explains if knowledge sharing influences employee performance. Shows an increase in employee performance if the company is getting better and if employees can convey criticism, ideas, and opinions to other members. Aristanto D. B.'s (2017) research results also state that knowledge sharing significantly influences individual innovation capability and individual performance. Knowledge-sharing activities will increase knowledge and motivate individuals to create innovations.

From the description of the independent variables, Community of Practice, Knowledge capturing, and Knowledge sharing allegedly affect the dependent variable, namely Employee Performance.

The conclusions of the hypothesis that can be built from the explanation above are:

H0: Community of Practice, Knowledge Capturing, and Knowledge Sharing do not affect the performance of PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor employees.

H1: Community of Practice affects the performance of employees of PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor.

H2: Knowledge Capturing affects the performance of employees of PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor.

H3 : Knowledge Sharing affects the performance of employees of PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor.

H4: Community of Practice, Knowledge Capturing, and Knowledge Sharing simultaneously affect the performance of PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor employees.

Based on this hypothesis, the conceptual framework of this research can be seen in figure 2.

III. METHODS

This study is a quantitative study with a causal dimension (causal effect), namely the analysis of facts that prove the influence of one variable on another variable. This study aims to determine the impact of the independent variables, namely community of practice knowledge management (X1), knowledge acquisition (X2), and knowledge sharing (X3), on the dependent variable (Y).

D. Definition and Operationalization of Variables

The operational definition indicates how to evaluate the variable, and then the researcher can find out whether the evaluation/measurement is good or bad. The functional purpose of this research is:

1) Knowledge Management

(1) Community of Practice

According to Masinambow (2016), an individual needs five (five) skills/ability to develop a community of practice, namely:

- Implementation methods.
- Share work stories.
- Share solutions to problems.
- Share work experiences with each other.
- Shaping behaviors and skills.

(2) Knowledge capturing

The acquisition of knowledge, in general, can be divided into 3 (three) stages. (Blair Cronin and others, 2018)

- Confirmation. This identification stage is the process of identifying tacit knowledge that is very important or very influential on the progress and success of the company, so it has to be recorded.
- Find. Next, gather knowledge in this process and make sure that expertise persists in the company. A good and effective strategy can be the basis of successful knowledge management.
- Gather. Gather the knowledge needed for the sustainability of the work and the effectiveness of the organization.

(3) Knowledge sharing

According to Kayes et al. in Hendri (2012), individuals need various abilities to share knowledge:

- Valuing different cultures
- Understand cultural complexities more quickly and understand how they can help create understanding/knowledge of new skills.
- Building relationships in history and culture
- Building connections or relationships with local communities can create new understanding and knowledge.
- Listening and observing
- Listening and observing skills can transform a person, learn more about local culture and existing practices, and understand the reasons behind these practices.
- Coping with Ambiguity
- Instead of seeing problems as confusing, they can see problems as new things that need to be learned.
- Translating complex ideas
- Good at presenting and explaining complex ideas in local language and meaning.
- Taking Action
- Performance skills and decision-making skills.

- Managing others

Expertise in allocating and managing local and foreign employees and resolving conflicts between them.

2) Employee Performance

Bernardin in pramiyudha (2018) suggests that there are at least six dimensions to measure/evaluate performance, namely:

- Quality is related to the process or results that are close to perfect/ideal in meeting the aims and objectives.
- Quantity relates to the unit of quantity or quantity produced.
- Timelines relate to the time it takes to complete an activity or produce a product.
- Cost-effectiveness relates to the level of use of organizational resources (people, money, materials, technology) in obtaining or obtaining results or reducing waste using corporate resources.
- Need for supervision related to individual skills to complete work or job functions without leadership assistance or supervisory intervention.
- Interpersonal impact is related to individual skills in increasing feelings of self-worth, goodwill, and cooperation among fellow workers and subordinates.

E. Population and Sample

This The population of this study was all employees of PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor, totaling 30 people. And all of them become research samples.

F. Method of Collecting Data

In this study, the authors use primary data and additional data. The primary data were obtained from questionnaires filled out by survey respondents. The Likert scale is used in the questionnaire for the research subject, namely PT PLN UPT.

G. Data Analysis Method

The data analysis method used is descriptive analysis method and multiple linear regression analysis using SPSS 25

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

H. Descriptive Analysis

The Twelve statements from 5 dimensions are used to determine the respondents' assessment of the community of practice PT. PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor. The average respondent on the Likert scale is 4, or 80% agree with the statement regarding the community of practice (Table 1).

Twelve statements from 5 dimensions are used to determine the respondents' assessment of Knowledge Capturing PT. PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor (The average respondent in the Likert scale is 3.7 or 74% agree with the statement regarding Knowledge Capturing (Table 2).

Twelve statements from 7 dimensions are used to determine the respondents' assessment of Knowledge Sharing PT. PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor. The average respondent on the Likert scale is 3.5 or 71% somewhat agree with the statement regarding Knowledge Sharing (Table 3).

Twelve statements from 6 dimensions are used to determine the respondents' assessment of the Employee Performance of PT. PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor. The average

respondent on the Likert scale is 3.7 or 75% agree with the statement regarding Employee Performance (Table 4)

I. Validity Test and Reliability Test

The validity test uses 5% significance, and the r-count must be greater than the r-table. From the validity test results, only seven community practice items have r counts greater than r tables. The rest are invalid and discarded from data analysis. Then, from the validity test results, only seven knowledge capturing items have r counts greater than r tables. The rest are invalid and discarded from data analysis.

Furthermore, from the validity test results, only seven knowledge-sharing items have r counts greater than r tables. The rest are invalid and discarded from data analysis. Finally, from the validity test results, only nine employee performance items have r counts greater than r tables. The rest are invalid and discarded from data analysis. Then for the reliability test using the Cronbach's Alpha method with decision making, if the Cronbach's Alpha value is more significant than 0.60, the questionnaire is considered reliable. Based on table 5, it can be seen that the four variables have Cronbach's Alpha values greater than 0.60, so they are considered reliable.

J. Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple Regression Analysis is helpful to determine the influence of the community of practice variables (X1), knowledge capturing (X2), and knowledge sharing (X3) on employee performance (Y).

Based on table 6 above, if this value is included in the multiple regression equation, then the following equation is obtained:

$$Y = 5.922 + 0.333(X1) + 0.041(X2) + 0.362(X3)$$

➤ The results of these equations can be explained as follows:

The constant (B1) of 5.922 means that if the three independent variables have no influence, the performance value is 5.922. The regression coefficient on the variable (B2) of 0.333 means that the community of practice variable will have a positive effect of 0.333 on performance. The regression coefficient on the variable (B3) of 0.041 means that the knowledge capturing variable will have a positive effect of 0.041 on employee performance. The regression coefficient on the variable (B4) of 0.362 means that the knowledge sharing variable will have a positive effect of 0.362 on employee performance.

K. Simultaneous Test (F Test)

A simultaneous Significance Test was conducted to see the effect of the community of practice, knowledge capturing, and knowledge sharing simultaneously on employee performance variables. Based on Table 7, it can be seen that the test results of F Count are 10,984. Because the value of F Count > F Table or 10,984 > 2.96, the hypothesis is accepted or community of practice, knowledge capturing, and knowledge sharing simultaneously affect employee performance variables.

L. Coefficient of Determination Test (R²)

The coefficient of determination test (R²), or the value of R square, is 0.559 or 55.9%. It can be concluded that the community of practice, knowledge capture, and knowledge sharing variables simultaneously affect the performance variable.

M. Hypothesis Test (t-test)

1) The Influence of Community of Practice on Employee Performance

Based on the hypothesis test (T-test), a community of practice has no significant effect on employee performance, and the t-count is 1.869, smaller than the t-table value of 2.056, so H1 is rejected.

Wenger (2015) suggests that knowledge creation in a community of practice occurs when someone shares the knowledge needed to solve problems. This is the basis for forming a pattern of knowledge sharing behavior and skill improvement so that it is closely related to the time of completion of work or the timeliness of work. From the explanation above, it can be seen that the employees of UPT PT PLN (Persero) Bogor are less motivated to share knowledge, which many factors can influence. Internal factors indicate that employees can play an active role in implementing community practices. This is supported by the results of community questionnaires on practical projects, which show outstanding results. However, in terms of external factors, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the performance of UPT PT PLN (Persero) Bogor employees.

2) The Effect of Knowledge Capturing on Employee Performance

Based on the hypothesis test (T-test), knowledge capturing has no significant effect on employee performance, and the t-count of 0.293 is smaller than the t-table value of 2.056 so that H2 is rejected (Table 8)

Based on Lumbantobing's 2016 statement, tacit knowledge is inherent in a person located in the brain or obtained through experience and work. Explicit knowledge is that all forms of knowledge are recorded and recorded for easy distribution and management. Employees of PT PLN (Persero) UPT Bogor have been able to use their gadgets to store the knowledge they have acquired, summarize new knowledge well, and control developing digital media to meet the needs of the current era of globalization. The knowledge to be obtained is often obtained from employees with longer tenure. Compared to new employees, relatively few employees have longer working hours. This can be proven by the characteristics of employees interviewed with more than ten years of service. Only 20% of them have insufficient resources to carry out knowledge acquisition resulting in poor results. New employees need to gain knowledge and experience from old employees because they have experienced complex work and solutions to all problems in completing their work.

3) The Effect of Knowledge Sharing on Employee Performance

Based on the hypothesis test (T-test), knowledge sharing has a significant effect on employee performance, and the t-count is 2.284, which is greater than the t-table value of 2.056, so H3 is accepted.

According to Aulawi's statement in Laily and Ernawati in 2020, knowledge sharing is a process where individuals exchange ideas and knowledge in an integrated manner and generate new understanding. The company and its employees share knowledge to set the company's goal of achieving a competitive advantage. In other words, in the knowledge-sharing process, employees exchange ideas, acquire a new culture, and create new understandings, which will impact the quality of employee performance. This can be seen from the results of the questionnaires that have been given, showing promising results. Employees feel that their work becomes easier after getting input from other employees to complete their work by company expectations quickly.

4) The Influence of Community of Practice, Knowledge Capturing, and Knowledge Sharing on Employee Performance

Based The simultaneous significance test results show that a community of practice, knowledge capturing, and knowledge sharing simultaneously affect employee performance variables. Therefore H4 is accepted.

Employee performance is one of the main factors for the progress of the company. Company performance also determines the sustainable development of a company. Community of practice, knowledge acquisition, and knowledge sharing can affect employee performance simultaneously, which is indirectly related to the company's survival. This has changed from knowledge management. The statement that new ideas develop into an increasingly common function in companies is consistent and has been the subject of various studies by companies as a way to find more effective ways to increase the company's competitive advantage (Zach in Zahid Zamir On Magazine, 2019)

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the explanation of the hypothesis, it can be concluded that only the knowledge sharing variable affects employee performance. Even so, the three variables simultaneously affect employee performance. The facts prove that knowledge sharing can significantly improve performance by exchanging ideas that generate new understanding. Therefore, UPT PT PLN (Persero) Bogor can organize various other programs to increase the intensity of employee exchange of ideas.

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List of Tables**Table 1 Descriptive Statistics for Community of Practice**

Dimension		Mean	Presentase
X1,1	Application of the method.	3,6	73%
X1,2	Share stories about work.	3,9	78%
X1,3	Share techniques to solve problems.	4,0	81%
X1,4	Share experiences about work.	4,1	83%
X1,5	The formation of behavior patterns, and improvement of skills	4,4	87%
Average		4,0	80%

Source: Processed Research Primary Data, 2021

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics for Knowledge Capturing

Dimension		Mean	Presentase
X2,1	The ability to capture knowledge	3,9	77%
X2,2	Reaction from knowledge capturing	3,9	77%
X2,3	Learning outcomes	3,7	75%
X2,4	Habit change	3,4	69%
X2,5	Organizational impact	3,8	75%
Average		3,7	74%

Source: Processed Research Primary Data, 2021

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics for Knowledge Sharing

Dimension		Mean	Presentase
X3,1	<i>Valuing different cultures</i>	3,4	67%
X3,2	<i>Building relationship within the hist cultures</i>	3,7	74%
X3,3	<i>Listening and observing</i>	3,2	63%
X3,4	<i>Coping with ambiguity</i>	3,9	78%
X3,5	<i>Translating complex ideas</i>	3,1	62%
X3,6	<i>Taking action</i>	3,7	75%
X3,7	<i>Managing others</i>	3,9	78%
Average		3,5	71%

Source: Processed Research Primary Data, 2021

Table 4 Descriptive Statistics for Employee Performance

Dimension		Mean	Presentase
X4,1	<i>Quality</i>	4,1	83%
X4,2	<i>Quantity</i>	3,3	66%
X4,3	<i>Timelines</i>	3,6	72%
X4,4	<i>Cost-effectiveness</i>	3,7	73%
X4,5	<i>Need for supervision</i>	3,9	77%
X4,6	<i>Interpersonal impact</i>	4,1	81%
Average		3,7	75%

Source: Processed Research Primary Data, 2021

Table 5. Reliabilty Test Result

Variable	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	Noted
<i>Community of Practice (X1)</i>	0,858	Reliable
<i>Knowledge Capturing (X2)</i>	0,805	Reliable
<i>Knowledge Sharing (X3)</i>	0,877	Reliable
Employee Performance (Y)	0,883	Reliable

Source: Processed Research Primary Data, 2021

Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression Result

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	<i>(Constant)</i>	5,922	3,723		1,591	0,124
	<i>Community Of Practice</i>	0,333	0,178	0,381	1,869	0,073
	<i>Knowledge Capture</i>	0,041	0,140	0,054	0,293	0,772
	<i>Knowledge Sharing</i>	0,362	0,174	0,389	2,084	0,047

Source: Processed Research Primary Data, 2021

Table 7. Simultaneous Test Result (F-Test)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	116,359	3	38,786	10,984	.000 ^b
	Residual	91,808	26	3,531		
	Total	208,167	29			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

b. Predictors: *(Constant), Knowledge Sharing, Knowledge Capture, Community Of Practice*

Source: Processed Research Primary Data, 2021

Table 8 Hypothesis Test (t-test)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	<i>(Constant)</i>	5,922	3,723		1,591	0,124
	<i>Community Of Practice</i>	0,333	0,178	0,381	1,869	0,073
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